

Role of animal, food, fungal protein containing vaccines, insulin injections and gastric acid inhibition therapy in the etiology of celiac disease

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Abstract

Celiac disease (CeD) is an immunological disorder that results in damage to the small intestine and is related to dietary gluten. Normally, the immune system develops a tolerogenic response to food proteins. Immune system exposure to food proteins in the absence of a danger signal results in a tolerogenic response. When a danger signal is present, the immune system can create an immunogenic response against food thus resulting in diseases such as celiac disease.

Antigluten antibodies (AGA), CD4+ T cells that recognize gluten peptides and antibodies against tissue transglutaminase (TG2) are involved in CeD.

CeD risk is increased following gastric acid inhibition therapy. Danger signals can be provided by ingested pathogens that survive passage through the stomach due to gastric acid inhibition therapy.

Yeast protein containing insulin injections and vaccines induce anti-saccharomyces cerevisiae antibodies (ASCA). The immune system is thus trained to recognize yeast as a dangerous parasite. Since the gut is colonized by yeast, ASCA results in inflammation and generation of danger signals.

Wheat protein containing vaccines induce antibodies against wheat proteins including gluten. The immune system is thus trained to recognize wheat as a dangerous parasite. Some gluten peptides survive gastrointestinal digestion. When such gluten peptides bind to these antibodies, the result is inflammation and generation of danger signals.

In all of the above cases, the danger signal and gluten proteins being simultaneously presented to the immune system in the gut, results in the induction of antigluten antibodies and activation of CD4+ T cells that recognize gluten peptides. TG2 forms TG2-gluten complex in the presence of gluten. TG2-gluten complex is a neoantigen which in the presence of a danger signal results in the induction of anti-TG2 antibodies. Thus resulting in CeD.

Gastric acid inhibition therapy is prescribed for gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD). Aeroallergen containing vaccines cause sensitization and priming of stomach mast cells. Subsequent ingestion of aeroallergen containing food results in GERD. Type 1 diabetes is induced by animal/plant protein containing vaccines and results in insulin dependence. Celiac disease is therefore a preventable iatrogenic disease. The solution is to immediately remove all non-target antigens from vaccines.

Introduction

Celiac disease is an immunological disorder that results in damage to the small intestine and is related to dietary gluten. Normally, the immune system develops a tolerogenic response to food proteins (1). Immune system exposure to food proteins in the absence of a danger signal results in a tolerogenic response. When a danger signal is present, the immune system can create an immunogenic response against food thus resulting in diseases such as celiac disease. Danger signals are generated when

pathogen associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) (2,3) are detected by the innate immune system. Danger signals are also generated by damaged or dying cells. These are damage associated molecular patterns (DAMPs) (4,5).

Antigliuten antibodies (AGA), CD4+ T cells that recognize gluten peptides and antibodies against tissue transglutaminase (TG2) are involved in celiac disease (6).

We know that the gluten specific CD4+ T cells are primed in gut draining lymph nodes. They express homing markers with gut homing potential(7,8). We also know that TG2 antibody levels decrease when on a gluten free diet (6).

Discussion

Why does the immune system produce an immunogenic response instead of a tolerogenic response towards gluten proteins? What caused the danger signal in the presence of gluten proteins?

Gastric acid inhibition

Acid reducing medications such as proton pump inhibitors (PPI) and histamine-2 blockers reduce gastric acid production. The result is natural food protein processing is impacted. Intact food proteins that would otherwise have been denatured are now transported to the gut. Many bacteria that would have been killed by stomach acid, survive and are also now introduced into the gut. Such bacteria trigger pathogen associated molecular pattern (PAMP) detectors that produce danger signals. With long term gastric acid inhibition therapy, the danger signal is constantly present, unlike the case with natural infections. The gut immune system is therefore now exposed to numerous food proteins and the danger signal. The result is an immunogenic response to food proteins which results in the development of food related immune disorders such as food allergies (9,10) and CeD.

Some gluten peptides survive gastrointestinal digestion even without gastric acid inhibition. With gastric acid inhibition, this only gets worse. Gluten peptides presented to the immune system in the gut along with a danger signal thus results in the synthesis of antigliuten antibodies (AGA) and activation of gluten specific CD4+ T cells. Since the immune system samples the gluten peptides in the gut in this case, the peptides are transported to the gut draining lymph nodes. Gluten specific CD4+ T cells are activated in the gut draining lymph nodes and are therefore imprinted with gut-homing markers.

Since TG2 is a self protein, the immune system has strong tolerance towards TG2. T cells that recognize TG2 would have been negatively selected in the thymus. However, in the presence of gluten, TG2 can form a TG2-gluten complex (6). This creates a neoantigen. Low affinity self reactive (LASR) T cells can recognize such neoantigens (11). In the presence of a danger signal, such T cells are activated, resulting in the synthesis of antibodies directed against TG2. Thus resulting in abrogation of peripheral tolerance to TG2.

This mechanism explains the development of celiac disease in patients using gastric acid inhibition therapy (12).

Since gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) for which gastric acid inhibition therapy is prescribed, is itself a vaccine induced disease (13), gastric acid inhibition induced celiac disease is a great example of the iatrogenic cascade at work.

Yeast protein containing insulin injections

Insulin may be produced using yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) (14). Therefore insulin injections contain residual yeast proteins. Predictably, type 1 diabetes (T1D) patients who have to routinely administer insulin injections, develop anti-saccharomyces cerevisiae antibodies (ASCA) (15). Injected proteins in general result in the development of IgE mediated sensitization directed against those proteins (16–19). Subsequent dietary exposure results in the synthesis of IgG4 antibodies directed against those proteins (20–23). This can result in diseases such as eosinophilic esophagitis (EoE) (24–27). Reducing dietary exposure to the protein results in lower specific IgG4 levels against that protein. A gluten free diet can also reduce dietary yeast protein exposure and reduce IgG4 ASCA levels. Gluten and yeast are found together in many baked foods.

Yeast is present in the gut. IgG4 ASCA result in eosinophil effector action against yeast in the gut thus resulting in chronic inflammation and host cell damage. This results in the generation of DAMP related danger signals. As described in previous sections, this danger signal along with gluten peptide exposure to the immune system, results in celiac disease. This explains ASCA's association with celiac disease (28–31). This also explains high IgG4 and eosinophil levels observed in celiac disease (27,32).

Since T1D itself is a vaccine induced disease (11,33,34), insulin injection induced celiac disease is yet another example of the iatrogenic cascade at work.

Wheat protein containing vaccines

Vaccines contain numerous food proteins including egg, milk, soy, peanut, gelatin, fish, wheat, (35,36) etc. Vaccines also contain either live viruses or aluminum adjuvant that produce the danger signal needed for the vaccine to work. However, this danger signal combined with injected food proteins, results in the development of IgE mediated food allergies (37–39). This is similar to gastric acid inhibition. In both cases, natural food protein processing is bypassed and food proteins are directly presented to the immune system along with danger signals.

Therefore wheat protein containing vaccines result in the development of IgE mediated sensitization to wheat proteins including gluten proteins. Subsequent exposure to dietary gluten results in synthesis of IgG4 directed against gluten proteins. Similarly, milk proteins in the vaccine cause IgE mediated sensitization to milk proteins. Subsequent exposure to dietary cow's milk results in synthesis of IgG4 directed against milk proteins. IgG4 directed against cow's milk proteins results in EoE. Cow's milk proteins are denatured by gastric acid and therefore there is very little milk protein transported to the small intestine. Therefore milk protein induced eosinophilic infiltration (EoE) is confined to the esophagus. In contrast, with gluten proteins, they can survive gastrointestinal digestion and be transported to the small intestine. Therefore a person making IgG4 against gluten can have eosinophilic effector action in the small intestine, resulting in inflammation and host cell damage, thus producing a danger signal. Therefore as before, the result is celiac disease. Eliminating cow's milk in the diet helps resolve cow's milk related EoE (26). Similarly, a gluten-free diet will result in lower levels of IgG4, lower eosinophil levels, along with improvement of CeD symptoms.

Yeast protein containing vaccines

Since yeast is present everywhere, it is an aeroallergen present in all vaccines (13). Yeast proteins are also specifically present in hepatitis B vaccines and human papilloma virus (HPV) vaccines as they are

derived from recombinant yeast (40,41). As in the case of insulin injection, these vaccines induce ASCA and consequently celiac disease.

Conclusion

Celiac disease is a preventable, iatrogenic disease. Non-target protein containing vaccines are the root cause of celiac disease. The ultimate solution is to immediately remove all non-target proteins from vaccines, using processes such as affinity chromatography (42). Japan removed gelatin from vaccines in 2000 as the ultimate solution to vaccine induced gelatin allergy (43,19). H1N1 nucleoprotein containing Pandemrix vaccine, induced narcolepsy in thousands (44–46). Even with two such high profile vaccine safety related disasters in the last two decades, vaccine makers and regulators have still not learned their lesson about the dangers of non-target protein contamination of vaccines.

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